

Spectrophotometric and Potentiometric Studies on Nickel Thiocyanate Complex

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The reaction between Ni^{2+} and CNS^- has been studied by spectrophotometric and potentiometric methods. The thermodynamic dissociation constant of the species NiCNS^+ has been determined at 25° by spectrophotometric method and at 35° by the potentiometric method using a concentration cell of the type:

From the experimental data, — ΔF , ΔH and ΔS for the formation of NiCNS^+ have been calculated which are 2048 cal. mole⁻¹, -13.17 K cal. and 51.1 cal. mole⁻¹ deg⁻¹ respectively at 25° .

Thiocyanate ion (CNS^-) is known to form complexes with various bivalent and trivalent metal ions. Franæus (*Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1953, 7, 21) studied nickel-thiocyanate system by extinctionometric method at 20° . The complexity constants for the species NiCNS^+ and $\text{Ni}(\text{CNS})_2$ were determined at sodium perchlorate concentration of 1.0M. In the present work the above system has been studied thoroughly by spectrophotometric as well as the potentiometric method. The dissociation constant of the NiCNS^+ species has been calculated at zero ionic strength with an idea to get the thermodynamic dissociation constant.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nickel perchlorate was prepared by adding an excess of nickel carbonate (E. Merck, G. R.) to dilute perchloric acid (E. Merck, G.R.). The solution was filtered and the nickel content was estimated by the dimethylglyoxime method.

B.D.H. 'AnalaR' sample of potassium thiocyanate was used as the ligand. It was estimated by Volhard's method (Vogel, 'Text-book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis', 2nd. ed., p. 256). All other chemicals used were of the reagent grade. The solutions were prepared in double-distilled water.

For absorption measurements Hilger-Watt's 'UVISPEK' spectrophotometer, model H 700-303, was used. The solutions were taken in quartz cells of 3 cm length. The readings were taken with cells interchanged as in our earlier work (Das and Aditya, this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 473). The optical measurements were taken at the room temperature which varied between 24° and 26° during the course of measurements.

For determination of stability constant of the complex, the absorbancies of solutions containing a fixed amount of nickel with varying concentrations of potassium thiocyanate were taken at wave lengths 660, 690, and 720 m μ . The concentration ranges of potassium thiocyanate were chosen with care such that the concentration of potassium perchlorate formed by the interaction of the reactants did not exceed its solubility limit,

In the potentiometric work, a Tinsley Vernier potentiometer was used for the E.M.F. measurements. The Ag, AgCNS | CNS⁻ electrode was prepared by the method suggested by Parida, Aditya, and Prasad (*ibid.*, 1952, 29, 377), improved upon by Vanderzee and Smith (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 721). For the potentiometric measurements concentration cells of the type,

were set up. The salt bridge was of the type used by Nath, Aditya and Prasad (*this Journal*, 1951, 28, 683). A saturated ammonium nitrate solution was used in the bridge. The arrangements were set up inside an air thermostat at 35°. Experiments were done in duplicate and the readings agreed within ± 0.2 mv.

TABLE I

Cell = 3 cm. Temp. = 25°.

Conc. of Ni ²⁺ (g. mole/litre).	Conc. of CNS ⁻ (g. mole/litre).	Optical density.		
		660 m μ .	690 m μ .	720 m μ .
0.06	0.05	0.475	0.456	0.502
0.06	0.06	0.476	0.467	0.508
0.06	0.07	0.496	0.476	0.512
0.06	0.09	0.515	0.500	0.530
0.06	0.10	0.531	0.515	0.542
0.06	0.12	0.545	0.527	0.550
0.06	0.14	0.570	0.540	0.570
0.06	0.15	0.576	0.547	0.577

K_d (from the data at 660 m μ) = 0.0338.

K_d (from the data at 690 m μ) = 0.0323. Average K_d = 0.0315.

K_d (from data at 720 m μ) = 0.0286

TABLE II

Temperature = 35°

Conc. of Ni ²⁺ (g. mole/litre).	Conc. of CNS ⁻ (g. mole/litre).	Mean E.M.F. (volts)	Ionic strength.	$K_d \times 10^2$.
0.10	0.10	0.02115	0.300	1.207
0.04	0.10	0.00915	0.168	0.247
0.07	0.08	0.01651	0.223	1.417
0.06	0.08	0.01450	0.200	1.433
0.05	0.08	0.01124	0.182	1.822
0.04	0.06	0.01124	0.144	1.672
0.04	0.08	0.01034	0.155	1.382
0.03	0.06	0.00901	0.120	1.563
0.03	0.03	0.01225	0.102	1.669
0.04	0.04	0.01301	0.134	1.826

Average K_d = 1.524 (± 0.045) $\times 10^{-2}$.

DISCUSSION

Spectrophotometric Method

The effect of addition of potassium thiocyanate on the absorption spectrum of nickel perchlorate in the visible was studied. Nickel perchlorate has an absorption

maximum at 730 m μ . The addition of CNS⁻ ion changes the absorbancy of the solution considerably although no appreciable change in the absorption maximum is observed. The change in absorbancy indicates reaction between Ni²⁺ and CNS⁻ ions. From the absorbancies of solutions containing nickel and thiocyanate ions, the stability constant has been calculated in the following manner.

The equilibrium between Ni²⁺ and CNS⁻ ions may be represented as

and higher complexes. For the present calculation only NiCNS⁺ species has been considered. The assumption is based on the fact that nickel halides are highly dissociated in solution. In the work on nickel acetate from this laboratory (this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 735) it has been shown that (in case of NiAc₂ in solution) the stage NiAc₂ $\rightarrow$ NiAc⁺ + Ac⁻, is practically complete. Therefore, for the present, let us consider the equilibrium,

Let C_1 and C_2 be the original concentrations of nickel perchlorate and potassium thiocyanate respectively and 'x', the concentration of NiCNS⁺ formed, ' d_1 ', the absorbancy of the solution with no thiocyanate in it, ' d_2 ', the absorbancy of a solution containing thiocyanate, and b_1 and b_2 , the extinction coefficient of the Ni²⁺ and NiCNS⁺ species respectively. Then we have,

$$d_1 = \epsilon_1 C_1 l \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$d_2 = \epsilon_2 x l + \epsilon_1 (C_1 - x) l \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

Combining equations 1 and 2, we get

$$x = \frac{d_2 - d_1}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1) l} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Substituting the expression (3) in the stability constant (K) expression, we have

$$\begin{aligned} K &= \frac{x}{(C_1 - x)(C_2 - x)} \times \frac{f_{\text{NiCNS}^+}}{f_{\text{CNS}^-} - f_{\text{Ni}^{2+}}} \\ &= \frac{x}{(C_1 - x)(C_2 - x)} \times \frac{1}{f_{\text{Ni}^{2+}}}, \\ \frac{C_1}{d_2 - d_1} &= \frac{1}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1) l} + \frac{1}{K(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1) l (C_2 - x) \cdot f_{\text{Ni}^{2+}}} \end{aligned}$$

According to the above equation, the slope and the intercept of the straight line on plotting $C_1/(d_2 - d_1)$ against $1/(C_2 - x) \cdot f_{\text{Ni}^{2+}}$ will give the value of the stability constant. Since f and x are not known, a series of approximation is done before the above equation can be utilised for obtaining a value of the association constant.

As first approximation x is taken to be equal to zero and $f_{\text{Ni}^{2+}}$ as unity, $C_1/(d_2 - d_1)$ is plotted against $1/C_2$. From the intercept, an approximate value of $(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)$ and ϵ_2 can be obtained, ϵ_1 being known from direct determinations. Having known ϵ_2 , the value of x can be calculated by using equation (3). This approximate concentration of the complex

will give an approximate value of the free reactants. From these approximate values, the ionic strength of the solution and hence an approximate activity coefficient $f_{\text{Ni}^{2+}}$ can be calculated. Now $C_1/(d_2 - d_1)$ is plotted against $1/(C_2 - x) f_{\text{Ni}^{2+}}$ to obtain a better value of ϵ_2 and hence the concentration of the complex. The ionic strength is calculated again and a better plot obtained. The process is repeated till constant values of the intercept and the slope are obtained. Incidentally, in the first rough plots, the points lie scattered and a mean straight line is drawn, but with two or at best three approximations, the points lie fairly well on a straight line. This further justifies our assumption regarding only one complex species.

Because of the lack of knowledge of the ionic radius, the Debye-Hückel equation could not be used in calculating the activity coefficient of ions. Instead, an alternative empirical relationship suggested by Davies (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 2093),

$$-\log f_i = 0.5 Z_i^2 \left\{ \frac{\mu^{\frac{1}{2}}}{(1 + \mu^{\frac{1}{2}})} - C\mu \right\}$$

where $C = 0.2$ and Z_i , the valency of the ion and μ , the ionic strength, have been used. The results are recorded in Table I. The average value of the dissociation constant of NiCNS^+ at $25^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ is 3.15×10^{-2} .

Potentiometric Method

Coming to the potentiometric measurements, the E. M. F. of the cell:

is given by the expression,

$$E = RT/F \ln \frac{a_1}{a_2},$$

where a_2 is the activity of the thiocyanate ion in the solution containing both potassium thiocyanate and nickel perchlorate solutions and a_1 , the activity in the solution containing no nickel ions, assuming that the liquid junction potential is negligible (practically eliminated by the use of the salt bridge). From the above expression, the activity of the CNS^- ion in solution can be calculated. The ionic strength of the solution was calculated by the method of approximation. As a first approximation, the concentration of the NiCNS^+ species is taken to be zero and the ionic strength of the solution estimated. Using the activity coefficient of thiocyanate ion at this ionic strength, the concentration of the free CNS^- ions is calculated. A knowledge of the free thiocyanate gives the concentration of NiCNS^+ formed and the free nickel ion in solution. With these more accurate estimation of the ionic strength is made. The process is repeated till a constant value is obtained for the ionic strength of the solution. The activity coefficients of the ions have been calculated on the basis of the equation, already mentioned, as was used in the calculation by using the spectrophotometric data. Thus having calculated the concentrations of the complex species, the association constant is evaluated. The results are recorded in Table II. The average value of the dissociation constant of NiCNS^+ complex, found by the potentiometric method, is 1.525×10^{-2} at 35° .

The potentiometric measurements have been made at 35° and the spectrophotometric ones at 25°. Although in the present investigation, we have not seen how the measurements by the two methods at the same temperature compare with each other, the agreement by the two methods is reported to be good. Franaeus (*Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1951, 5, 139) studied the complex formed between Cu^{2+} and NO_2^- ions at 20°, using spectrophotometric as well as potentiometric methods. The former method gave a value of 1.30 and the latter 1.23 for the logarithm of the formation constant. A similar agreement has been observed in the case of Fe^{3+} - CNS^- complex (Betts and Dainton, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5721; spectrophotometric method, $\log K_1 = 2.94$; Lawrance, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1956, 52, 236; potentiometric method, $\log K_1 = 3.03$). So from our results at 35° and 25°, we have calculated the constant at 20° because we thought it might be interesting to compare our results with that of Franaeus, who determined the equilibrium constant from the same complex at 20°. Our value comes out to be 0.0456 at 20° and zero ionic strength, whereas Franaeus's value is 0.0666 at the same temperature but at an ionic strength of 1 *M*. It is not possible to assess the quantitative effect of this difference in ionic strength. Nevertheless, since the increase in ionic strength is likely to increase the dissociation constant, this difference is qualitatively justified.

From our results, the standard free energy change ($-\Delta F$) for the reaction

comes out to be 2.048×10^3 cal. mole⁻¹ at 25° and 2.563×10^3 cal. mole⁻¹ at 35°. The value of $-\Delta H$, for the formation of NiCNS^+ , is -13.17 Kcal. mole⁻¹ and ΔS , for the formation at 25° is 51.1 cal. mole⁻¹. deg.⁻¹.

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